

METHODOLOGY AND CONCEPT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

In this article we are following this principle ensures the ability to communicate in a language already at the earliest stages of learning, which is reinforced by mastering the skills of written communication.

There is no single universal methodology for teaching a foreign language that takes into account individual characteristics, goals, and duration of training.

I strongly recommend a teaching method that is a synthesis of traditional technology (grammar-translation methodology) and modern Western and domestic developments in this area.

In favor of using a synthesis of various methods, the optimality and universalization of the method was well said by the famous methodologist P. Hagboldt: "A person who claims that his method is the best, scientific and at the same time the fastest method of language acquisition is similar to a doctor advertising a universal medicine from all diseases. This method can only cause a condescending or sad smile, because it resembles a loud advertisement placed in every Sunday newspaper: "I teach French, German and Spanish in twenty hours" [1]. A similar idea belongs to L.N.Tolstoy, who wrote: "There is not a single method that is bad or good, the disadvantage of a method is only in the exclusive adherence to one method."

Communication principle. Training is organized in the modeling of natural communicative situations that constantly arise in our lives. For successful modeling, the following conditions must be met:

1) Statement of the problem - the selection of material should be problematic. This stimulates students' logical and creative thinking and thereby stimulates their speech activity.

2) Heuristic - the student spontaneously reacts to speech stimuli.

3) Informativeness and novelty - the use of material that is of interest to the learner.

Axioms.

Any statement must be:

1) motivated, it should be based on the internal need of the student to express his opinion.

2) Situationally determined (suitable for a specific situation)

3) Dialogical, if the situation requires it.

The principle of interconnected teaching of types of speech activity - the simultaneous formation of four types of speech activity occurs:

- speaking
- listening
- reading
- letter

The principle of professional orientation of training. When selecting material, the occupation and professional interests of students are taken into account. Communication between people exists mainly in oral form, therefore it is advisable at the initial stage of training to pay attention to speaking and understanding speech by ear, which will ensure successful mastery of writing and reading skills.

Following this principle ensures the ability to communicate in a language already at the earliest stages of learning, which is reinforced by mastering the skills of written communication.

In modern pedagogical theory and practice, the problem of developing students' personal activity is especially relevant. Currently, the attention of many teachers is attracted to the issues of organizing conditions under which learning would proceed most successfully, as well as issues related to the formation of persistent positive motivation of students to learn, the creation of conditions for personal growth and the development of cognitive interests of schoolchildren.

As a multidimensional education, the teaching method has many sides. For each of them, methods can be grouped into systems. In this regard, many classifications of methods appear, in which the latter are combined on the basis of one or a number of common characteristics.

Teaching method includes the principles and methods used by teachers to teach students. These strategies are determined partly by the subject of study and partly by the nature of the learner. For a particular teaching method to be appropriate and effective, it must match the characteristics of the learner and the type of learning it is intended to provide. There are proposals for the development and selection of teaching methods that should take into account not only the nature of the subject, but also how students learn [3].

The trend in modern schooling is that it encourages a lot of creativity. It is a known fact that human advancement occurs through reasoning. This reasoning and original thought enhances creativity. Approaches to teaching can be broadly classified into teacher-centered and student-centered. In the teacher-centered approach to learning, teachers are the central figure in the model. Students are viewed as "empty vessels" whose primary role is to passively receive information (through lectures and direct instruction) with the ultimate goal of testing and assessment. The main task of teachers is to impart knowledge and information to their students. In this model, teaching and assessment are viewed as two separate entities. Student learning is measured through objectively assessed tests and assessments [4].

In the Student-centered learning approach, while teachers are the authority figure in this model, teachers and students play an equally active role in the learning process. The primary role of the teacher is to teach and facilitate student learning and overall understanding of the material. Student learning is measured through formal and informal

forms of assessment, including group projects, student portfolios, and class participation. Learning and assessments are linked; Student learning is continuously measured during teacher training [4]. Commonly used teaching methods may include lesson participation, demonstration, reading, memorization, or combinations thereof.

Around 3000 BC, with the advent of writing, education became more self-conscious or self-reflective, with specialized professions such as scribe and astronomer requiring specific skills and knowledge. Philosophy in ancient Greece led to issues of pedagogical method entering the national discourse. In his literary work, *The Republic*, Plato described a system of education that he believed would lead to an ideal state. In his dialogues, Plato described the Socratic method, a form of inquiry and debate designed to stimulate critical thinking and illuminate ideas. Since then, many educators, such as the Roman Educator Quintilian, have sought to find specific, interesting ways to encourage students to use their intellect and help them learn. Comenius in Bohemia wanted all children to study. In his *The World in Pictures*, he created an illustrated textbook that children would be familiar with in everyday life, and used it to teach children. Rabelais told how Gargantua's student learned about the world and what is in it. Much later, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, in his book "Emile," presented a method for teaching children the elements of science and other subjects. During the Napoleonic Wars, the teaching methods of Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi of Switzerland allowed refugee children from a class considered out of reach to learn.

He described this in his report on the educational experiment in Stanza. The Prussian education system was a compulsory education system dating back to the early 19th century. Parts of the Prussian education system served as models for education systems in a number of other countries, including Japan and the United States. The Prussian model required that classroom management skills be included in the teaching process [5]. Compulsory education laws require children to attend school at a certain age. School districts also have a responsibility to ensure the safety of students while they are in their care. New teaching methods may include television, radio, internet, multimedia and other modern devices. Some educators believe that the use of technology, while facilitating learning to some extent, is not a substitute for educational methods that encourage critical thinking and the desire to learn. Query learning is another modern teaching method. A popular teaching method used by the vast majority of teachers is hands-on learning. Hands-on activities are activities that require movement, talking and listening and activate multiple areas of the brain. "The more parts of your brain you use, the more likely you are to retain information," says Judy Dodge, author of *25 Rapid Formative Assessments for the Differentiated Classroom*.

The task of a modern school is to form a comprehensively developed personality. According to the Law "On Education", the purpose of education is "The comprehensive development of the individual as the highest value of society, the development of his talents, mental and physical abilities, the cultivation of high moral qualities, the formation of citizens capable of conscious social choice, the enrichment on this basis of intellectual, creative, cultural potential of the people, increasing the educational level..." [3].

In our opinion, achieving this goal is possible only if there is an optimal choice of teaching methods. Since the main activity of a schoolchild is learning, it is only through the use of rational teaching methods that students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as the formation of a worldview, the development of abilities, and the implementation of

educational, educational and developmental functions of education. A method is a tool in the hands of a teacher, which serves not only to introduce certain truths into children's heads, but also to guide children's observation and thinking as they study objects and environmental phenomena. So, we are convinced of the leading importance of teaching methods in the organization of the educational process. The concept of "method" is the ordered methods of interconnected activities of the teacher and students, aimed at solving educational problems. In didactics, a teaching method is a certain way of purposefully implementing the learning process and achieving a set goal. The correct selection of methods according to the purpose and content of training, age characteristics, students contributes to the development of their cognitive abilities, equipping them with the skills and abilities to use the acquired knowledge in practice, prepares students for independent acquisition of knowledge, and shapes their worldview.

Method is the art of the teacher to direct the thoughts of students in the right direction and organize work according to plan. The structure of the method includes: the content of training, ways to achieve the goal, student activity, methodological techniques, purpose, methods, tasks, tools, means, rules, pedagogical skills of the teacher.

Thus, the method is the main tool of pedagogical activity; only with its help is the learning product produced and the interaction between teacher and students is carried out.

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